

»» NEWSLETTER ««

dairy_{4.0}

Advanced, trustworthy AI and data solutions for individualised automated milking & feeding of dairy cows

Co-funded by the European Union

Project funded by
Schweizerische Eidgenossenschaft
Confédération suisse
Confederazione Svizzera
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Federal Department of Economic Affairs,
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State Secretariat for Education,
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This work has received funding from the Swiss State Secretariat for Education, Research and Innovation (SERI)

»»» CHALLENGE

The dairy industry, vital to the EU economy, faces challenges with rising global demand and CO₂ emissions. Automated Milking Systems (AMS) and Automated Voluntary Milking Systems (AVMS) are vital. AI-driven advancements are needed to enhance efficiency, animal health, milk quality, and feeding strategies.

“The International Farm Comparison Network (IFCN) reports that despite fewer dairy farms, those remaining will grow larger to meet rising global demand. Technological advancements aim to reduce emissions per kilogram of milk by 28% by 2050.”

»»» SOLUTION

dAlry 4.0 integrates AI, Data, and Robotics to optimize AVMS, reducing environmental impact. It focuses on individual cow health monitoring via AVMS and introduces a laser sensor for real-time milk quality analysis. These innovations allow personalised milking, tailored feeding, and milk partitioning by quality, demonstrated in real-world cases.

- **Automated health assessment while exploiting data from both the AVMS and activity sensors on the animal**
- **Development and integration of a novel milk analyzer for at-line milk quality assessment**
- **Upgraded individualization of milking settings**
- **Upgraded individualization of the forage-to-concentrate ratio and quantity of concentrate in AVMS, for more efficient automated monitoring of nutrient balance per animal**
- **Development of a novel Decision Support System (DSS) based on new simulation models, and Digital Twin of farm providing individualised decision support for stakeholders.**

During the first 12 months of the project, significant progress was made in several key areas:

»»» Use cases detailed definition

We successfully defined detailed use cases, leveraging input from partners and stakeholders to ensure they align with real-world needs and project goals.

»»» User & stakeholder requirements

Comprehensive requirements were collected and analysed from users and stakeholders, forming a solid foundation for system development

»»» System requirements and conceptual designs

We defined detailed use cases, leveraging input from partners and stakeholders to ensure they align with real-world needs and project goals.

»»» Action plan for clustering with EU projects & services

A strategic action plan was established to foster collaboration and knowledge exchange with other EU projects & services, ensuring synergy and maximizing impact. First try to connect **dAIry 4.0** with EU projects was with **BROMEDIR project** (<https://bromedir.eu>), also an EU-funded project, focusing on sustainable farming enabling continuous on-farm monitoring of milk sample on nutritional value and health traits.

»»» Data infrastructure

We developed the initial version of the data infrastructure, which serves as the backbone for collecting, storing, and managing project-related data. This foundational framework will support seamless integration of data from farms and sensors ensuring scalability and reliability for future iterations.

TECHNICAL UPDATES COMING NEXT

- First versions of all novel, AI-driven modules
- Initial version of the integrated robot
- Comprehensive real-world validation protocol

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12M Consortium Meeting

A successful **dAlry 4.0** meeting was held on 13th-14th November 2024 in Maassluis, Netherlands hosted by the project partner LELY. The two-day meeting was a great opportunity for all partner teams to discuss the project progress in detail.

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Tour of LELY farm

On the second day, LELY organized a tour of its farm. This insightful visit gave partners the opportunity to see a milking robot in action. The tour was invaluable for helping partners understand the adjustments needed to integrate all modules into the milking robot during the first integration phase.

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Córdoba 24-26 abril 2024

ANEMBE 2024

dAIry 4.0 participated in ANEMBE 2024, showcasing its innovative approach to advancing the dairy industry through IoT, AI, and data-driven solutions

Digital and emerging technologies for competitiveness and fit for the green deal

- Inteligencia artificial, datos y robótica (robot de ordeño):
- Mejora la Salud y el Bienestar Animal
 - La Calidad de la leche
 - Optimizar la Alimentación

Automated Voluntary Milking System (AVMS)

CVPR 2024 / xAI-2024

dAIry 4.0 was also represented at CVPR 2024 and xAI-2024 by our partner ICCS, highlighting its cutting-edge research in explainable AI and computer vision applications for agriculture

arXiv - eprint - arXiv:2406.00298
Electrical Engineering and Systems Science > Image and Video Processing

Submitted on 1 Jan 2024
Complex Style Image Transformations for Domain Generalization in Medical Images
Nikolaos Spanos, Anastasios Arsenos, Paraskevi Antonia Theodidou, Paraskevi Tzouros, Athanasios Voulodimos, Stefanos Kollias

The absence of well-structured large datasets in medical computer vision results in decreased performance of automated systems and, especially, of deep learning models. Domain generalization techniques aim to approach unknown domain data sources. In this paper we introduce a novel framework, named ComStyle, which leverages style transfer and adversarial training, along with high-level input complexity augmentation to effectively expand the domain space and address distributions. State-of-the-art style transfer methods depend on the existence of subdomains within the source dataset. However, this can lead to an inherent dataset bias in the image creation. Input-level augmentation can provide a solution widening the domain space in the source dataset and boost performance on out-of-domain distributions. We provide results from experiments on semantic segmentation on prostate data and corruption robustness on cardiac data which demonstrate the effectiveness of our approach. Our method increases performance in both tasks, without added cost to training time or resources.

Comments: Accepted at IEEE/CVF Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition Conference Workshops (CVPRW) 2024
Subjects: Image and Video Processing (eess.IV), Computer Vision and Pattern Recognition (cs.CV)
Cite as: arXiv:2406.00298 [eess.IV]
(or arXiv:2406.00298v1 [eess.IV] for this version)
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2406.00298>

arXiv - eprint - arXiv:2401.11609
Computer Science > Machine Learning

Submitted on 21 Jan 2024 (v1), last revised 18 Apr 2024 (this version, v3)
Graph Edits for Counterfactual Explanations: A comparative study
Angeliki Dimitriou, Nikolaos Chaidos, Maria Lymperakou, Giorgos Stamou

Counterfactuals have been established as a popular explainability technique which leverages a set of minimal edits to alter the prediction of a classifier. When considering conceptual counterfactuals on images, the edits requested should not concepts present in the input data. At the same time, conceptual distances are defined by knowledge graphs, ensuring the optimality of conceptual edits. In this work, we extend previous endeavors on graph edits as counterfactual explanations in a comparative study which encompasses both supervised and unsupervised Graph Neural Network (GNN) approaches. To this end, we pose the following significant research questions: should we represent input data as graphs, which is the approach in terms of performance and time efficiency to generate minimal and meaningful counterfactual explanations for black-box image classifiers?

Subjects: Machine Learning (cs.LG), Artificial Intelligence (cs.AI)
Cite as: arXiv:2401.11609 [cs.LG]
(or arXiv:2401.11609v1 [cs.LG] for this version)
<https://doi.org/10.48550/arXiv.2401.11609>

Journal reference: The World Conference on Explainable Artificial Intelligence (XAI 2024)

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Adra-e forum #ADRF24

At **ADRF24**, Lely represented the **dAlry 4.0** project, showcasing how Data, Robotics, and AI are transforming dairy farming to enhance animal welfare, improve farmer well-being, and reduce CO₂ emissions. The event emphasized Europe's commitment to advancing innovation and competitiveness in AI, Data, and Robotics for a sustainable future.

Web Summit 2024

dAlry 4.0 showcased its groundbreaking integration of IoT, AI, and data analytics at **Web Summit 2024** in Lisbon, highlighting advancements in dairy productivity, animal welfare, and product traceability. The event provided an excellent platform for networking, exploring collaborations, and sharing insights on transforming the dairy industry through technology.

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Wrapping up our second newsletter edition, we're thrilled by the progress within our **dAlry 4.0** project.

Our vision for sustainable agriculture propels us forward.

With gratitude to our partners, we stride into the future, eager to pioneer advancements in dairy farming.

Stay tuned for updates as we revolutionize the field though technology and commitment.

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Follow us!

@dAlry40

MEET THE CONSORTIUM

CYRIC

UAB

Universitat Autònoma de Barcelona

TECHNISCHE UNIVERSITÄT WIEN

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